

O‘ZBEK ZAMONAVIY RAQS SAN’ATINING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI

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Kalit so‘zlar: raqs, usul, qobiliyat, badiiy mahorat, faoliyat, jarayon, baletmeyster, raqqosa, harakat, san’at, kompozitsiya, ko‘cha raqsi, popping, breking, hip-hop, “Fidjital dance”.

ЭТАПЫ СТАНОВЛЕНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ УЗБЕКСКОГО СОВРЕМЕННОГО ИСКУССТВА ТАНЦА

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Аннотация: В данной статье автор предоставляет информацию о современном танцевальном искусстве, видах, этапах становления и развития современного танцевального искусства Узбекистана, творческих коллективах.

Ключевые слова: танец, метод, способности, артистическое мастерство, деятельность, процесс, балетмейстер, танцор, движение, искусство, композиция, уличный танец, поппинг, брейкинг, хип-хоп, “Fijital dance”.

STAGES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK CONTEMPORARY DANCE ART

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Abstract: In this article, the author provides information about modern dance art, types, stages of formation and development of modern dance art in Uzbekistan, and creative groups.

Key words: dance, method, abilities, artistic skill, activity, process, choreographer, dancer, movement, art, composition, street dance, popping, breaking, hip-hop, “Fijital dance”.

Uzbek dance art was formed on the basis of national folk dance and European dance art. It is known about national dance that the first information about this art form appeared in the 10th-11th centuries. Dances of this period were mainly based on movements that imitate the world of various animals, birds and plants. Today we can see them in folk and stage dances based on Uzbek dance schools. The European network can also be divided into two areas: ballet and modern dance. We have enough information about the art of ballet and its formation in Uzbekistan. However, there is very little information about the formation and development of modern dance. If we look at the history of the cultural life of our country, we can see information about the beginning of the 20th century. It was the time when some forms of modern pop art appeared. In particular, types of circus and amusement shows aroused interest among the population and began to acquire their fans. These were wonderful variety and circus acts, adapted for performance on stage, distinguished by an original artistic solution of various genres, a wealth of interesting tricks. Acrobats, jugglers and tightrope walkers combined their various tricks with dance elements, creating complex movements.

Not only circus performances, but also various dances of the "modernized" style, enriched with circus elements, began to appear on the European stage. The repertoire of Russian circuses, which began to come to Turkestan in the 80s of the XIX century, included dance numbers. At the end of the century, F. A. Yumatov, one of the famous organizers of circus performances in Turkestan, had a team

consisting of Russian and foreign artists. Later, their ranks were replenished with Uzbek actors - famous clowns and entertainers. In 1913, the Coliseum Theater was built in Tashkent, owned by G. M. Sinsadze, a local entrepreneur and philanthropist. It is worth noting that this Coliseum Theater has a restaurant with a stage for a variety show in the shape of European cities, where along with musicians and singers modern dance performers often perform.

At the end of the 19th century, amateur troupes, various theatrical, choreographic and musical societies were created in Tashkent, Samarkand, Kokan, Margilon and other cities to promote modern achievements of European art, including the art of dance, and to organize creative meetings. Thus, the activities of these theatrical, concert and circus creative groups gave Turkestanis the opportunity to join the arts, especially the development of the art of dance. In 1932, the State Musical-Variety-Circus Society was created under the People's Commissariat of Public Education of Uzbekistan. All private concert groups in the republic joined this association. As a result of the development of concert activities in Uzbekistan and support for creative groups from the state, great things have been done. New musical, vocal and dance works performed by young artists from Uzbekistan appeared in their repertoire. In 1954, the Uzbek State Variety Art Association was established under the Ministry of Culture of Uzbekistan, and in 1972, the activities of the variety group, which became the first in the East and the third in the Union, under the leadership of Botir Zakirov played an important role in the development of Uzbek variety art. In particular, B. Zokirov invited a new team to the ballet troupe of the Ballet Troupe named after. Thus, variety art and modern dance art began to form on the basis of Uzbek variety art. In the 1980s, modern ballroom dance ensembles began to form at the palaces of culture and art operating in different regions and cities of our country. For example, V.P. It is worth mentioning such groups as the disco club "Gramophone" of the Tashkent Aviation Production Association named after Chkalov, "Yoshlik (Youth)" under the direction of the Turchin family couple, the ensemble "Modern Choreography and Plastic" under the direction of Lili Sevastyanova, "Fantasy". During their

creative career, they won the applause of the public with many concert programs. They took part in prestigious republican and international competitions, became laureates and received diplomas. They managed to go on tour around the republic and foreign countries with their creative programs. In particular, the attention of the public was soon attracted by "Fantasy" and many other dance ensembles organized under the direction of an experienced dancer and choreographer Sergei Alexandrovich Fedorov in the Palace of Culture "Khimik" in the city of Fergana. They returned as laureates of international festivals and competitions held in Turkey, Bulgaria and Germany.

How important is contemporary dance as an art?

Isadora Duncan, an American dancer and founder of free dance, believed that "everyone should be taught to dance, it should be a 'natural state' for people." The importance of contemporary dance is that it helps to reduce tension in the human psyche and body. Contemporary dance is the key to this freedom. It helps a person express themselves and can have a therapeutic effect for some people. It encourages a person to be physically active, learn something new, relieve stress and express themselves. Contemporary dance can be mastered at any age, because this dance is, first of all, a dance of emotions. It provides self-development, progress, free movement of a person, striving for a goal, flexibility of body and mind.

Contemporary dance techniques correspond to the naturalness and energy of a person, since they provide greater flexibility and mobility than ballet. The most characteristic feature of contemporary dance is the natural lines of body position, it has more freedom, the boundaries of this style are much wider than jazz and especially classical dance. For example, modern street dance arose from the peculiarities of social and cultural conditions of different regions. In particular, break and hip-hop emerged in New York and quickly became a cultural phenomenon along with DJing, rap and graffiti.

Today, some types of modern dance art have formed in Uzbekistan, each with its own characteristics.

1. Breaking is a complex and dynamic type of dance that includes many acrobatic elements. However, it is completely wrong to consider it as a collection of physical and athletic tricks. This style requires the ability to hear, feel and play music, as well as artistic skill.

The history of break dancing in our country differs from many other modern types of dance. This style of dance is actively developing in the capital, even in the Fergana and Samarkand regions. In 2014, the first competitions of the international competition "RedBull BC One" were held on the stage of the Ilkhom Theater.

It should be noted that this year it has been included in the Summer Olympics program for the first time.

2. Hip-hop style. Unlike break dancing, hip-hop emphasizes expression, flexibility and smoothness, allowing artists to freely express their emotions through dance. Sergey Zlotnikov, who opened his own dance school in 2005, is considered one of the popularizers of hip-hop in Uzbekistan.

Sergey Zlotnikov and his team have repeatedly participated in organizing events, starred in videos of domestic and foreign performers, and participated with their work in television shows. S. Zlotnikov also founded the dance group "Double Touch", in which many famous Uzbek dancers working in various styles of dance art grew up.

Currently, Yan Li and Vladimir Meshcheryakov actively demonstrate hip-hop in Uzbekistan and take prizes at the largest competitions in Central Asia.

3. Popping style - the "Electric Boogaloos" team is the founder and popularizer of popping in Uzbekistan. The main feature of the dance in this style is a sharp contraction of muscles. Over time, popping began to mean other substyles, for example, the dancer's movements resemble a wave-like and smooth flow of water, or it is distinguished by the imitation of the movement of a robot.

4. Dancehall style - appeared in Jamaica in the 70s with a high-speed version of reggae. The style is focused mainly on movements and steps in the pelvic area. Dancehall includes elements of hip-hop and twerking dance styles. At the same time, the dance performance can be both joyful and aggressive.

5. K-Pop style - the uniqueness of this style is that it is a Korean dance style.

K-Pop dances are performed in groups of three to seven people. If in hip-hop or pop music you can improvise, then in K-Pop all the movements are set in advance by a choreographer. The K-Pop dance culture appeared in Uzbekistan five years ago. There are currently many teams, the most famous of which are Agma, Encore, Pikachu, STC, KND. The Korean Embassy in Uzbekistan plays an active role in promoting this dance style.

In addition to the listed styles, from mod and waacking to krap, locking and other styles are actively developing in Uzbekistan. Experienced dancers try not to limit themselves to one style, even when performing within one style, they use other dance styles.

There are two types of street dancing: demonstration and competition. These dance styles bring people together - dancers get to know each other and evaluate their skills at demonstration performances and competitions.

During the demonstration of their skills, the participants take turns going to the center of the dance floor. This is not a competition, but a demonstration of their performance skills and level. There will be no judges, all the dancers will support each other.

The competition is a creative competition between individual participants, couples or groups of dancers. At the same time, auditions are held both among representatives of a certain style and by category of all styles. These competitions are held on the basis of certain criteria and rules, requirements and often divide the participants by level (from beginner to professional) or age. In team performances, each participant takes turns showing their skills, and the judges evaluate the overall performance. These competitions often use pre-prepared combinations of movements that emphasize teamwork and synchronicity. Another feature of the competition is that none of the dancers know in advance what music they will dance to.

Another special direction of modern dance is modern fashionable dance, which was formed not on the streets, but in clubs. This style arose from the

imitation of the gait, pose and image of the model, so much attention is paid to the clothes that are worn when performing a dance to a certain music.

" Fidjital dance " is a type of sports competition "Games of the Future", which is gaining popularity in our country. "Fidjital dance" is a combination of physical movement and computer activity. The dance attracts many participants, since it does not require special training, and dance shows are held in the form of dance competitions. Today, in order to develop phytosport and select athletes for the national team of Uzbekistan to participate in prestigious sports competitions, the 1st Republican Championship in Phytodance "Just Dance" is held. The winning teams of the regional stage will take part in the national stage, and the national team of Uzbekistan will be formed from athletes selected as the most talented. Members of the selected national teams will take part in the sports competitions "Games of the Future-2025", which will be held in the United Arab Emirates in 2025.

The art of dance arms a person with high taste and gives him spiritual food. Today, the art of modern Uzbek dance has become one of the main areas of choreography. The task of industry specialists, using modern knowledge and advanced technologies, to spiritually and aesthetically educate the younger generation. In order to prepare qualified specialists, the State Academy of Choreography of Uzbekistan has opened an educational direction 60211600-Choreography (Modern Dance). Qualified specialists are engaged in the education and professional training of students in this field of education. All teachers-choreographers and ballet masters constantly conduct creative research so that modern Uzbek dance art wins its positions at the international level along with the Uzbek national dance art. We believe that the professional duty of each teacher is to responsibly approach the consideration and implementation of the tasks set before industry specialists by the head of our state on the formation of a mature generation, the use of talented youth, the formation of their managerial qualities.

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